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Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF HYPOMAGNESEMIA IN DIABETICS OF
BAHAWAL VICTORIA HOSPITAL, BAHAWALPUR: A CASE
CONTROL STUDY**¹Anam Laraib, ²Dr Noor ul Ain Fatima, ³Jawairia Altaf¹Quaid e Azam Medical College Bahawalpur²IHO 205 RB, PHFMC, Faisalabad³Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Hyperglycemia usually causes a multifactorial disorder called as Diabetes. Diabetes, poor control and hypomagnesemia are closely associated. Insulin receptor is affected by magnesium levels. In patients of diabetes, hypomagnesemia is involved in resistance of insulin through the interference of insulin receptor integration. Inactive insulin receptor phosphorylation is responsible for this. Hypomagnesemia is added to resistance of insulin in the cells. Hypomagnesaemia has been associated significantly with the development and aggravation of the severity of type 2 as well as type 1 diabetes. Its implications in the severity of the disorder can be drastically reduced by administration of magnesium fortified diets to diabetic patients. Furthermore, future researches should further probe into the scope of hazardous implications of hypomagnesaemia in diabetics in order to alleviate the complications.

Keywords: Frequency, Hypomagnesemia, Diabetcs, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Case Control.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is a multifactorial disorder portrayed by hyperglycemia. Studies have demonstrated that magnesium levels are brought down in patients of diabetes contrasted with non-diabetic controls¹. There has been a critical relationship between the hypomagnesaemia and poor diabetic control and its consequent confusions over Diabetes Mellitus⁴. Comprehensively more than 300 million individuals experience the ill effects of DM and the prevalence is anticipated to ascend to 600 million upon the finishing of the following decade². Since 1940's it has been bolstered that type 2 DM is related with hypomagnesemia². Magnesium assumes a key part in Insulin receptor affectability. Insulin under typical conditions prompts glycogen generation in the liver, lipid union by fat tissue and glucose take-up in muscle. Insulin resistance is regularly the outcome of lessened affectability of Insulin Receptor that is made out of 2 Insulin *a*Subunits and two *b* subunits³. Hypomagnesaemia amongst diabetic patients has been embroiled in insulin resistance by meddling in the integrity of Insulin receptors. This occurs because of dormancy of the insulin receptor phosphorylation and is therefore viewed as the fundamental system by which hypomagnesaemia adds to insulin resistance in cells⁶.

Glucose take-up in skeletal muscles is done with the upregulation of GLUT4 glucose transport protein mechanism⁸. In a current report done in rats with streptozotocin initiated diabetes, magnesium supplementation expanded GLUT4 articulation in rodent muscles and along these lines brought serum glucose levels down to typical range³. Besides the unfriendly impacts of the hypomagnesaemia in type 2 diabetes (fundamentally interfering Insulin receptor sensitivity), hypomagnesaemia likewise prompts disabled emission of insulin by means of pancreatic B cells and along these lines is additionally ensnared in type 1 DM. In pancreatic B- Cells, Mg²⁺ particles specifically impact the rate of glucokinase action by going about as cofactor for adenine nucleotides⁹. Our study centers upon the recurrence and power of hypomagnesaemia among diabetic patients (Type 1 and type 2) and its connection to the glycemic record.

Over the previous decades, hypomagnesaemia has been firmly connected with type 2 DM. Patients with T2 DM and hypomagnesaemia enter an endless loop in which hypomagnesaemia causes insulin resistance. The various reasons for low magnesium levels in diabetics incorporate eating regimens too in magnesium, Osmotic Diuretics causing high renal discharge of Mg, Insensitivity to Insulin Affecting intracellular Mg. Magnesium lack may likewise pay vital part in endothelial breakdown.

Hypomagnesaemia happens at an occurrence of 13.54 to 47.7% among patients of type 2 diabetes. Poor dietary admission, autonomic brokenness, adjusted insulin digestion, glomerular hyper filtration, osmotic diuresis, intermittent metabolic acidosis, hypophosphatemia and hypokalemia might be contributory. It has been connected to poor glycaemia control, coronary vein ailment, and hypertension, diabetic retinopathy, and neuropathy, nephropathy and foot ulceration. It is intriguing to take note of that autonomous examinations have announced a higher frequency of hypomagnesaemia in ladies contrasted and men 12 (2:1).

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY:

Our sample size consists of 59 cases of diabetic patients & 24 non diabetic controls. Our questionnaire consists of multiple questions regarding life style & complications they face during their illness. It is a case control study and we collected the blood samples from the patients of BVH (Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital), Bahawalpur, and the duration of our study was from 15 June 2016 to 10 August 2017. We collected the patient's blood samples. Blood samples were then centrifuged with the help of a centrifuge machine at 3000rpm. The serum was then collected in the eppendorf tube. We numbered the eppendorf tubes accordingly. Patient's names and the normal control person's name were also mentioned on the tubes. Then we came to the final procedure which was to conduct the test on the samples. The magnesium levels were checked in the pathology department of BVH, Bahawalpur, and the data eventually analyzed through SPSS version 20.

RESULTS:

	Cases		Controls N=23 (mean $\pm$ SE)
	Type I N=12 (mean $\pm$ SE)	Type II N=47 (mean $\pm$ SE)	
Serum Glucose (Random)	334.4 $\pm$ 46.8	253 $\pm$ 16.8	104 $\pm$ 1.4
HbA1c	11.9 $\pm$ 0.9	12.6 $\pm$ 2.9	5.8 $\pm$ 0.1
Mg	1.5 $\pm$ 0.1	1.8 $\pm$ 0.3	2.0 $\pm$ 0.1

Table 1. Shows the magnesium levels, random sugar levels and glycosylated hemoglobin levels (HbA1c) of the cases and controls. We clearly get an idea from the table that the cases display a mild to moderate decrease in magnesium levels as compared to controls. HbA1c levels closely correlate with the magnesium levels in serum. A good glycemic control i.e. (5.8 amongst the controls) correlates with fairly good levels of magnesium in body (2mg/dl). On the other hand poor glycemic control amongst diabetics (a high HbA1c of 11.9 in type 1 and 12.6 in type 2 diabetics) causes profound hypomagnesaemia of 1.5mg/dl and 1.8 mg/dl respectively.

Glucose levels amongst diabetic patients clearly showed an alarming increase of glucose levels in type 1 and type 2 diabetics. A state of hypomagnesaemia amongst our cases thus indicates a positive correlation between the severity of the diabetes and the status of hypomagnesaemia. A state of normal glucose levels and greater than or equal to 2mg/dl magnesium levels amongst controls clearly establishes the role of hypomagnesaemia implicated in diabetes. A reduction of magnesium levels is noted both in type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes, indicating that magnesium is needed not only for the synthesis of insulin but also plays an important role in insulin receptor sensitivity

Literature review:

In an examination directed in Libya, "*Determinants of Hypomagnesaemia in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus*". The Magnesium Concentration In this short examination was 0.74 ± 0.10 mmol/L. Patients utilizing metformin, proton pump inhibitors and β adrenergic receptor agonists showed lessened plasma Mg²⁺ levels. In our base control examine, the outcomes are (1.5 ± 0.1) for type 1, (1.8 ± 0.3) for type 2 and (2.0 ± 0.1) for controls.

In an examination led in United Kingdom "*Investigation of Serum Mg level in Type 2 diabetes and its connection with glycosylated hemoglobin*" patients (38%) had low serum Mg level (< 1.8 mg/dl). There was no major change observed amongst the new patients and the already admitted patients (41% versus 35%, $P = 0.38$).

In an investigation case control study about "*Hypomagnesaemia in Type 2 Diabetes is correlated with Insulin Resistance*". The mean age and standard deviation of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus chosen for this examination was 50.5 ± 11.2 . The mean age and SD of sound controls subjects was 46.8 ± 11.7 . Serum level of magnesium has been found by a few examiners to associate conversely with fasting blood glucose concentration and the concentration of HbA1c. The present examination uncovered that a higher predominance of hypomagnesaemia was found in patients having HbA1c $> 7\%$ and FBS > 130 mg/dl.

In an interventional study "*Diabetes is the main factor accounting for hypomagnesemia in obese subjects*" the serum Mg levels for Type 2 diabetes were 0.75 ± 0.07 contrasted to our study where Mg levels for type 2 diabetes were 1.8 ± 0.3 . There was no huge contrast in between the two.

In another study conducted in Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences Jamshoro, Hyderabad (LUMHS) Pakistan named "*Hypomagnesaemia in patients with diabetes mellitus*" regarding the geographical distribution of the diabetic patients, 76% people belonged to rural areas. There was no big difference in between this study and our study. Another variable, the mean random blood glucose level was 220.52 ± 13.68 (SD) in hypomagnesaemia diabetic contrasted to our study where for type 1 diabetes the glucose level is 334.4 ± 46.8 while for type 2 it is 253 ± 16.8 .

DISCUSSION:

Mg is an intracellular cation, less than 2% of total body concentration in ECF. Various studies have shown that magnesium deficiency is a possible novel risk factor for type 2 diabetes. Multiple observational studies have been conducted like "*the Atherosclerosis risk in community*" it clearly demonstrated the strong relation between low serum Mg level and type 2 diabetes. Likewise multiple Invitro studies have demonstrated the effect of magnesium on the Insulin secretion by the pancreas and on insulin responsiveness by peripheral tissues.

In our study, the type 1 diabetics have Mg level (1.5 ± 0.1) and type 2 diabetics have (1.8 ± 0.3) . serum magnesium level of diabetic patients showed significant negative correlation with duration of disease glycemic control as measured by HbA1c and near significant negative correlation with fasting blood sugar. No significant correlation were found between Mg²⁺ level, BMI or age. In our study, the HbA1c values for type 1 along with SD is (11.9 ± 0.9) and for type 2 (12.6 ± 2.9) & for controls 5.8 ± 0.1 . Hereby, Magnesium supplementation prevents diabetes occurrence in a rat model to develop spontaneous type 2 diabetes. Multiple clinical studies have demonstrated that daily Magnesium intake can improve the short term insulin response and handling in diabetic patients. In diabetes, there is direct relationship between serum Mg level and cellular glucose disposal which is independent of insulin secretion¹⁰. The change in glucose disposal has been shown to be related to the increased sensitivity of tissue to insulin in presence of ad Mg²⁺ is intracellular cation, under 2% of aggregate body content present in ECF different investigations have demonstrated that magnesium inadequacy is a conceivable novel hazard factor for type 2 diabetes. A few observational investigations like the atherosclerosis hazard in group have shown solid affiliation however low serum Mg²⁺ level and type 2 diabetes. In vitro considerations have demonstrated an impact of magnesium on the discharge of Insulin by the pancreas and on the responsiveness to insulin by fringe tissues.

In our investigation, the type 1 diabetics have Mg level (1.5 ± 0.1) and type 2 diabetics have (1.8 ± 0.3) . Their discoveries are steady with the consequences of (7,10,11), serum magnesium level of diabetic patients demonstrated huge negative relationship with length of ailment glycemic control as measured by HbA1c and close critical negative connection with FBS. No huge relationship were found however Mg²⁺ level and BMI or age. In our examination, the the HbA1c value

for type 1 along with SD is (11.9 ± 0.9) , for type 2 is (12.6 ± 2.9) and for controls 5.8 ± 0.1 . Thus we see that the Magnesium supplementation halts the advancement of diabetes in a rodent of previously unconstrained type 2 diabetes. A few clinical intercessions have exhibited that day by day Magnesium supplementation can enhance here and now insulin reaction in diabetic individuals⁶. In diabetes, there is an immediate relationship between serum Mg level and cell glucose transfer which is free of insulin secretion¹⁰. The adjustment in glucose transfer has been appeared to be identified with the expanded affectability of tissue to insulin in nearness of sufficient magnesium level¹².

CONCLUSION:

Hypomagnesaemia has been associated significantly with the development and aggravation of the severity of type 2 as well as type 1 diabetes. Its implications in the severity of the disorder can be drastically reduced by administration of magnesium fortified diets to diabetic patients. Furthermore, future researches should further probe into the scope of hazardous implications of hypomagnesaemia in diabetics in order to alleviate the complications.

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